

Catalytic thermo-chemical production of solvent and fuel grade hydrocarbons from polyethylene and polypropylene plastic wastes

Version 1

Description

The purpose of the Data Management Plan (DMP) is to efficiently collect, store, analyze and share data at all the stages of research project implementation while ensuring compliance with the legal and ethical requirements. DMP will be utilized to organize and manage obtained data for successful achievement of the project goals and activities. Main aim of the Project is to investigate the potential of innovative solvent-free two-step catalytic hydrotreatment (HT) for polyolefin wastes conversion into solvent and fuel grade hydrocarbons over new synthesized Ru based catalyst(s). The technology can contribute to plastic waste amount reduction by providing new efficient chemical recycling option, which corresponds to circular economy approach. The main objectives of the project involve (1) screening tests of commercial Ru catalysts on two-step HT process; (2) development of new reusable Ru supported catalyst(s); (3) optimization of two-step catalytic conversion technology of polyolefin wastes for solvent and fuel grade hydrocarbon production; (4) determination of the fuel properties of produced hydrocarbons. DMP will include experimental data regarding to structure analyzation of novel Ru supported catalysts; composition analysis of produced liquid and gaseous hydrocarbon mixtures via hydrotreatment from plastic wastes.

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LCS

Grant

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Researchers

Kristaps Malins (0000-0002-9727-0730), Ilze Malina (0000-0002-2301-9674)

Organizations

Riga Technical University

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [Catalytic thermo-chemical production of solvent and fuel grade hydrocarbons from polyethylene and polypropylene plastic wastes](#)

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[Ilze Malina \(0000-0002-2301-9674\)](#)

Organizations:

[Riga Technical University](#)

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: [LCS](#)

Grants: [lzp-2024/1-0456](#)

Project:

3. License

License: [CC-BY-4.0](#)

Access Rights: [Public](#)

Publication Date: [2025-02-01](#)

4. Templates

Descriptions

Analysis data of Ru supported catalysts structure

Following description is devoted to experimental data of structure investigation of novel Ru supported catalysts. Novel Ru supported catalysts will be synthesized by different methods (strong electrostatic adsorption, successive impregnation, deposit-precipitation etc.). Their structure will be analyzed by common analytical techniques. DMP will include raw data of X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis and N₂-sorption isotherms of synthesized catalysts. These data are necessary to investigate and understand catalyst structure-activity relationships and to determine most appropriate synthesis method for Ru supported catalysts.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The aim of the data acquisition is to analyze synthesized novel Ru supported catalysts structure properties by analytical methods (XRD, N₂-sorption analysis) and therefore determine structure-catalyst activity relationships. Obtained data will help to accomplish objective (2) about development of new reusable Ru supported catalyst(s). The data will be acquired using the scientific equipment

available at the Institute of Chemistry and Chemical Technology of the Faculty of Natural Sciences and Technology of RTU.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Experimental data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- PDF
- XLS
- JPG

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

400

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

No I have not considered re-using any of existing data, because there are not any. Data generated in research project will be novel.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Data might be useful to other reserarchers, which develops new metal supported catalyts.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

Metadata containing simple sentences will describe what is seen in the data.

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

No

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

Until the scientific publications are published.

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

RTU research data repository

RTU research data repository is founded by our organisation.

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Internet Browser

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2028-01-01

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

2029-01-01

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Ilze Malina (0000-0002-2301-9674)

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

Passwords

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

Analysis data of produced liquid hydrocarbon mixture

Following description is devoted to experimental data for composition investigation of liquid hydrocarbon samples produced by hydrotreatment from plastic wastes. Polyolefin plastics produces wide range of liquid linear and isomerized hydrocarbons (C5-C32) under hydrotreatment conditions in the presence of Ru based catalysts. DMP will include experimental data – chromatograms of liquid hydrocarbon samples. Gas chromatograph-mass spectrometer (GC-MS) will be used to obtain chromatograms. These data are necessary to determine best performing catalysts and conditions for obtaining highest liquid hydrocarbon yield from plastic wastes.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The aim of the data acquisition is to analyze produced liquid hydrocarbon mixture composition by GC-MS method. Obtained data will help to accomplish objective (1) about development of new reusable Ru supported catalyst(s) by systematically analyzing obtained liquid hydrocarbon composition in the presence of each catalyst. The data will be acquired using the scientific equipment (chromatographs) available at the Institute of Chemistry and Chemical Technology (RTU).

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Experimental data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- PDF

- XLS

- JPG

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

400

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

No I have not considered re-using any of existing data, because there are not any. Data generated in research project will be novel.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Data might be useful to other scientists conducting research about linear saturated hydrocarbon production from plastic wastes.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

Metadata containing simple sentences will describe what is seen in the data.

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

No

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2028-01-01

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

2030-01-01

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Ilze Malina (0000-0002-2301-9674)

GC-MS data of produced liquid hydrocarbon samples will be collected, described by metadata, organized and imported to repository by Ilze Malina.

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

Passwords

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3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

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No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

Analysis data of produced gaseous mixture

Following description is devoted to experimental data for composition investigation of gaseous samples produced by hydrotreatment from plastic wastes. Ru catalysts are known of its high cracking activity under hydrotreatment conditions, therefore gaseous hydrocarbons such as CH₄, C₂H₆, C₃H₈, C₄H₁₀ and gases CO₂, CO are produced as well. DMP will include experimental data – chromatograms of gaseous samples produced from plastic waste hydrotreatment. Gas chromatograph- thermal conductivity detector (GC-TCD) will be used to obtain chromatograms. These data are necessary to determine best performing catalysts and conditions for obtaining highest liquid hydrocarbon yield from plastic wastes.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The aim of the data acquisition is to analyze produced gaseous mixture composition by GC-TCD method. Gases such as CO₂, H₂, CO and light hydrocarbons (CH₄-C₄H₁₀) will be analyzed. Obtained data will help to accomplish objective (1) about development of new reusable Ru supported catalyst(s) by systematically analyzing obtained gaseous mixture composition in the presence of each catalyst. The data will be acquired using the scientific equipment (chromatographs) available at the Institute of Chemistry and Chemical Technology (RTU).

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Experimental data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- PDF
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1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

200

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

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1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

No I have not considered re-using any of existing data, because there are not any. Data generated in research project will be novel.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Data might be useful to other scientists conducting research about gaseous hydrocarbon production from plastic wastes.

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